

Synthesis and characterization of tris[*N*-(2-oxo-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]-manganese(III) and its reaction products with oxygen, nitrogen and/or sulphur donors

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Abstract : Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate reacts with *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine (ohglH₂) in methanolic solution in (1 : 3.5) molar ratio yielding the complex, tris[*N*-(2-oxo-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]manganese(III), [Mn^{III}(ohglH)₃] and its reaction with other oxygen, nitrogen and/or sulphur donors results in the Mn^{III} complexes having compositions [Mn^{III}(ohgl)(L)(X)] [L = salicylate (sal), X = H₂O, pyridine (py); 4-nicotinate (nic), X = H₂O] and [Mn^{III}(ohgl)(ohdtb)(Y)₂].H₂O [ohdtb = *o*-hydroxydithiobenzoate, Y = H₂O, py, 3-picoline (3-pic)]. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, cyclic voltammetry, NMR, electronic and infrared spectral studies. On the basis of UV, IR and NMR spectral evidences, the ligand, *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine, exists predominantly in the quinoneamine form and acts as monobasic bidentate and dibasic tridentate ligand in the complexes.

Keywords : Manganese(III), sulphur donor, polyfunctional ligands.

Manganese is known to play several important roles in biological processes¹, e.g. in superoxide dismutase^{2,3} and an azide insensitive catalase⁴. Manganese complexes in high oxidation state are potentially used as oxidizing agents, catalysts⁵ and electro catalysts⁶ for the oxidation of compounds such as alcohols, ethers and waters^{7,8}. On the other hand, manganese in photosystem-II is of particular interest where manganese in higher oxidation state functions as a catalyst for oxidizing two molecules of water to molecular oxygen^{9,10}. While EXAFS data¹¹ indicate that only N and O donor atoms are bound to manganese, there is no evidence for a manganoporphyrin centre in OEC. In the coordination environment of non-porphyrinic, N,O donors, species are of interest in the biomimetic chemistry of the water oxidation site of photosystem-II¹². The elucidation of the roles of manganese in biological processes in general and photosynthetic system particular have stimulated interest in the formation, photochemistry and chemical properties of compounds containing manganese in high oxidation states. The coordination chemistry of manganese is dominated by stable manganese(II) and manganese(III) centres and a mononuclear Mn^{III} centre has been established at the active site of some enzymes that display superoxide dismutase activity¹³. The possibility of a

binuclear centre in the catalase isolated from *Lactobacillus plantarum* has also been proposed¹⁴. A range of unsymmetrical Schiff base complexes of manganese(III) have been reported¹⁵⁻²¹ which generates molecular oxygen in photolysis action of PS-II of the green plant.

Keeping in view the importance of manganese complexes in higher oxidation states, synthesis and characterization of manganese(III) complexes from polyfunctional *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine and its reaction products with oxygen, nitrogen and/or sulphur donors have been investigated and are being reported here.

Results and discussion

The complexes isolated in the present study, together with their colour, decomposition point, analytical data, magnetic moment and molar conductance are presented in Table 1. The analytical data and stoichiometries of the complexes reveal the formation of complexes of Mn^{III} of the compositions [Mn^{III}(ohglH)₃] (**1**); [Mn^{III}(ohgl)(L)(H₂O)] [L = salicylate (sal) (**2**)/4-nicotinate (nic) (**3**); [Mn^{III}(ohgl)(sal)(py)] (**4**); [Mn^{III}(ohgl)(ohdtb)(A)₂].H₂O [A = H₂O (**5**), py (**6**) or 3-pic (**7**)]. The complexes are brown coloured. They are air stable in solid state and do not decompose up to 300 °C. All the complexes (**1-7**) are

Table 1. Analytical data, magnetic moment and molar conductance data for ohglH₂ and its complexes

Ligand/Complex (colour)	Percentage of yield (%) (decom. temp. °C)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				μ_{eff} (B.M)	ΔM ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1})
		Mn	C	H	N		
ohglH ₂ (Reddish brown)	70 (120)	-	68.49 (68.12)	4.84 (4.80)	5.89 (6.11)	-	-
[Mn(ohglH) ₃] (1) (Brown)	57 (> 300)	7.28 (7.44)	63.29 (63.60)	3.62 (3.67)	5.60 (5.71)	4.82	2.10
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(sal)(H ₂ O)] (2) (Brown)	80 (> 300)	12.35 (12.57)	55.46 (55.03)	3.49 (3.44)	3.10 (3.21)	4.80	2.40
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(nic)(H ₂ O)] (3) (Brown)	76 (> 300)	13.30 (13.00)	54.59 (54.16)	3.28 (3.33)	6.50 (6.65)	5.05	3.20
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(sal)(py)] (4) (Brown)	76 (> 300)	11.10 (11.04)	59.89 (60.36)	3.57 (3.62)	5.79 (5.63)	4.85	4.50
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O (5) (Brown)	60 (> 300)	10.90 (10.42)	47.19 (47.62)	3.83 (3.77)	2.70 (2.78)	5.20	3.80
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(py) ₂].H ₂ O (6) (Brown)	60 (> 300)	9.50 (9.67)	58.00 (57.51)	4.60 (4.63)	6.81 (6.71)	5.15	3.00
Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(3-pic) ₂ .H ₂ O (7) (Brown)	60 (> 300)	8.54 (8.11)	46.29 (45.87)	4.19 (4.13)	6.40 (6.42)	5.05	4.50

moderately soluble in methanol and acetonitrile but are readily soluble in strongly coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO.

The weight loss experiments for the complexes were carried out by heating a small amount of sample in a glass tube for 4 h in an electric oven maintained at 100, 180 and 220 °C. Only the complexes (5-7) show loss of weight at 110 °C corresponding to one water molecule suggesting that they possess one water molecule in their lattice structure. On the other hand, the complexes (2) and (3) show weight loss corresponding to one water molecule while the complex (5) shows weight loss corresponding to two water molecules at 180 °C suggesting the presence of coordinated water molecules in the first coordination sphere around the metal centre. The complex (4) shows weight loss corresponding to one pyridine molecule per metal center, while the complexes (6) and (7) show weight loss corresponding to two pyridine/3-picoline molecules per metal center at 230 °C. The expulsions of these donor molecules at high temperature suggest that they are coordinated to the metal centre.

The molar conductance values of the complexes in methanol lie in the range 2.1 to 4.50 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating their non-electrolytic nature in this solvent²².

Magnetic moment :

All the complexes have μ_{eff} values in the range

4.80 to 5.20 B.M. which are in good agreement with manganese(III) complexes²³.

Tautomeric structure of ligand (ohglH₂) :

The ligand *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine is expected to exist in naphtholimine form as similar to *N*-salicylidene-glycine but a comparison of UV spectra of potassium *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinate (λ_{max} 415 nm, ϵ 8817 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹; λ_{max} 345 nm, ϵ 1006 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and potassium *N*-salicylidene-glycinate (λ_{max} 410 nm, ϵ 985 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹; λ_{max} 330 nm, ϵ 9185 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) in ethanol revealed that these compounds exist predominately as quinoneamine and phenolimine respectively²⁴. The ligand *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine also shows bands λ_{max} 418 nm, ϵ 6050 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹; λ_{max} 403 nm, ϵ 5710 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹; λ_{max} 298 nm, ϵ 4870 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The band at λ_{max} 418 nm, ϵ 6050 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ is characteristic of quinoneamine form of the ligand while other bands arise due to *n*- π and π - π^* transitions²⁴.

The quinoneamine form of *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinate is further supported by its ¹H NMR spectra in DMSO-*d*₆, which showed clearly the presence of =CH-NH-CH₂- grouping. The signals of =CH- and >CH₂ protons are doublets centred at δ 9.17 and 2.67 ppm respectively. In view of the occurrence of these doublets, the broad multiplet observed at δ 13.71

ppm must necessarily be assigned to the NH proton of quinoneamine form. The naphthyl -CH- protons in the ligand appear as multiplet in the region 7.33–8.47 ppm. Since even weak signals for naphtholimine form could not be detected in the spectra, thus it should be concluded that quinoneamine form vastly predominates in solution as shown in Fig. 1. Quinoneamine form for related ligands such as *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)amines has also been suggested²⁵.

Fig. 1

Infrared spectral data also strongly support the quinoneamine form of the ligand. The spectra of *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine showed a strong band at 1638 cm^{-1} , with no other band at higher frequency in the double band region, may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of the quinoneamine form after considering the UV and NMR spectral evidences. This $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band position is much lower than their normal range and such low carbonyl stretching frequency cannot be accounted for adequately on the basis of conjugation and internal hydrogen bonding. Thus the contribution of the tautomeric form, naphtholimine, seems probable. As a result, the structure of the ligand, is interpreted as to exist in tautomeric naphtholimine form (I) and quinoneamine form (II) as shown in Fig. 1. The infrared spectra of analogous compounds such as 1-phenylazo-2-naphthalenol²⁶ and 1-nitroso-2-naphthalenol²⁷ also show lower carbonyl stretching frequencies at 1625 and 1620 cm^{-1} , respectively for which zwitterionic contributing structures are possible as similar to immonium naphtholate form of the present ligand. Two strong bands presumably due to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ are observed at 1607 and 1400 cm^{-1} , respectively. The $\Delta\nu$ of 207 cm^{-1} can be taken as evidence for strong hydrogen bonding of NH with carboxylate ion²⁸ and due to this the quinone oxygen can form only a weak bifurcated hydrogen bond, if at all. The ligand shows a broad band extending from 3500–2300 cm^{-1} with splitting at 3186, 3093, 2886 cm^{-1} suggesting strongly intramolecular hydrogen bonded NH. The medium intense band at 1545 cm^{-1} , amidst bands due to skeletal vibration of the aryl ring, is attributable to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$.

It is important to note that *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine exist⁵ in the quinoneamine tautomeric form

(II) (Fig. 1) and so the aromaticity of the condensed aryl rings compromised. The greater stability of this form over the naphtholimine form appears due to partly to contribution from zwitterionic immonium naphtholate form and partly to strong internal hydrogen bonding under resonant conditions. Displacement of tautomeric equilibrium towards quinoneamine form on passing from *N*-salicylidene bases to their bicyclic homologues may be attributed to the fall in redox potential of the corresponding quinone²⁹.

Tautomeric structure of ligand in metal complexes :

The electronic spectra of the metal chelates reveal that 418 nm band of ohglH_2 is shifted only marginally. This is indicative of the quinoneamine structural form of the ligand in the metal complexes also²⁴.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the ligand, *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine shows a band at λ_{max} 418 nm (ϵ 6050 $\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) which is characteristic of quinoneamine form of the ligand. Other bands at 298 nm (ϵ 4870 $\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), 403 nm (ϵ 5710 $\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) are assigned to arise due to $n-\pi^*$ and $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions²⁴. These bands are shifted marginally to longer wave lengths in the complexes and appear in the region 290–490 nm. This suggests the bonding of the ligand to the metal centre.

Usually Mn^{III} has a 5D electronic ground state and in a pure octahedral symmetry, a single absorption band is expected due to the spin-allowed transitions $^5E_g \rightarrow ^5T_{2g}$. However, even for symmetrical ligand fields they are subjected to John-Teller distortions³⁰ (high spin d^4 configuration) and three absorption bands are expected due to $^5B_{1g} \rightarrow ^5A_{1g}$, $^5B_{1g} \rightarrow ^5B_{2g}$ and $^5B_{1g} \rightarrow ^5E_g$ transitions as the distortion is an elongation of the *Z*-axis of D_{4h} symmetry. The first band ($^5B_{1g} \rightarrow ^5A_{1g}$) usually occurs in the near IR region³⁰ and is not generally observed while the other two bands are observed in the region 410–600 nm. All the Mn^{III} complexes under present study show two bands in the region 422–589 nm (Table 3) except complex (6) which shows only one band at λ_{max} 595 nm , are assigned to $^5B_{1g} \rightarrow ^5B_{2g}$ and $^5B_{1g} \rightarrow ^5E_g$ transitions³¹. The bands for which extinction coefficient values are large cannot be assigned to *d-d* transition bands and hence these bands may be assigned to charge-transfer bands, probably due to $\text{Mn}(d\pi) \rightarrow \pi^*$ (azomethine)³² in complexes (1-4). Bands observed in the region 290–390 cm^{-1} with high extinction coefficient values in the complexes (5-7) are assigned to charge transfer bands probably due to $\text{Mn}(d\pi) \rightarrow \pi^*$ (azomethine)³² and/or

$Mn(d\pi) \rightarrow \pi^*$ (dithioligand).

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectrum of free ligand shows a broad band extending from 2300–3500 cm^{-1} with splitting at 3186, 3093, 2886 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of hydrogen bonded NH. This band almost completely conceals bands due to $\nu(C-H)$. The IR spectrum of $[Mn(ohglH)_3]$ (**1**) shows strong broad band in the region 2300–3600 cm^{-1} similar to that of the free ligand indicating presence of $>NH$ group in the coordinated ligand while all other complexes (**2-7**), show a strong broad band in the region 3429–3440 cm^{-1} assignable to coordinated or lattice water or due to free -OH group of salicylate. These complexes do not show strong broad band in the region 2500–3300 cm^{-1} indicating coordination through deprotonated amino nitrogen atom of quinoneamine form of the ligand.

Quinone carbonyl band^{26,33} at 1638 cm^{-1} in free ligand is observed either one or two strong bands in the region 1636–1692 cm^{-1} in complexes (**1**, **5-7**), suggesting no coordination of quinone carbonyl group of the ligand to the metal centre in these complexes. This band is found missing in the spectra of the complexes (**2-4**), however the strong $\nu_{as}(COO)$ band in the region 1590–1600 cm^{-1} with a shoulder in the region 1621–1625 cm^{-1} is found which is likely the carbonyl band of the ligand, shifted through coordination. The ligand also contains a shoulder band at 1545 cm^{-1} assignable³⁴ to $\nu(C=N)$ which shifts to lower wave number in its complexes by about 3–38 cm^{-1} indicative of coordination to metal centre through nitrogen atom of group $>C=N$.

The carboxylic group of $ohglH_2$ shows $\nu_{as}(COO)$ and $\nu_s(COO)$ bands at 1607 and 1400 cm^{-1} , respectively with $\Delta\nu$ of the order 207 cm^{-1} suggesting strong intermolecular hydrogen bonding involving NH group with carboxylate ion²⁸. The corresponding $\nu_{as}(COO)$ and $\nu_s(COO)$ bands in the complex $[Mn(ohglH)_3]$, are observed at 1590 and 1400 cm^{-1} respectively. The other complexes also show $\nu_{as}(COO)$ and $\nu_s(COO)$ bands in the ranges 1586–1600 cm^{-1} and 1367–1394 cm^{-1} with $\Delta\nu$ in the range 190–230 cm^{-1} which is quite reasonable for suggesting monodentate coordination of carboxylato group of the ligand in the form $ohglH^{1-}$ and $ohgl^{2-}$ ions²⁸. The complexes containing salicylate or 4-nicotinate ion show $\nu_{as}(COO)$ and $\nu_s(COO)$ bands which are mixed with that of $ohgl^{2-}$ ion but showing shifting towards lower frequencies indicative of uninegative bidentate chelating behaviour of the ligand. The non-involvement of phenolic group of salicylate ion in bonding is inferred from the appearance of $\nu(C-O)$ (phenolic) in

the same region(1100–1260 cm^{-1}) for complexes and free salicylate group.

The complexes containing *o*-hydroxydithiobenzoate show in-plane O–H bending mode broad band in the region 1361–1367 cm^{-1} which appears for free ligand at 1379 cm^{-1} suggesting non-involvement of -OH group in bonding^{28,35,36}. Its uninegative bidentate chelating nature in the complexes (**5-7**), has been ascertained by appearance of a strong single band in the region 992–930 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu(C-S)$ ³⁵. The complexes (**4**, **6** and **7**), show characteristic bands of coordinated pyridine or 3-picoline²⁸.

The low frequency bands observed in the region 455–521, 356–369 and 247–297 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu(M-N)$, $\nu(M-O)$ (quinone carbonyl) and $\nu(M-O)$ (carboxylato), respectively³⁷. It has been reported that the position of these bands depend on the nature and number of other ligands present³⁸. The important IR bands are given in Table 2.

All the above spectral data indicate that *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine acts in its metal complexes as monobasic bidentate through carboxylate oxygen and amino nitrogen and dibasic tridentate through its quinone oxygen, deprotonated amino nitrogen and carboxylate oxygen.

Cyclic voltammetric study :

The cyclic voltammogram of the manganese(III) complexes (**1**) to (**7**) were measured in acetonitrile solution using a platinum electrode containing 0.1 *M* tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP).

The current potential curves for the manganese(III) complexes (**5**), (**6**) and (**7**) shows reversible/quasi-reversible peak at $E_{1/2}$ -332 to -485 mV region (vs SCE). The wave can be assigned as Mn^{III} to Mn^{II} reduction³⁹. The separation of the peak potentials between the cathodic wave and corresponding anodic wave for both redox waves lies in the region 72 to 173 mV, which indicate its reversibility or quasi-reversibility.

However, the complexes (**1**), (**2**) and (**3**) do not show any reduction/oxidation peak corresponding to Mn^{III} to Mn^{II} or Mn^{III} to Mn^{IV} . But the complex (**4**) shows an irreversible one electron reduction at the cathodic side of the standard calomel electrode around -340 mV. This cathodic peak can be assigned as one electron irreversible reduction from Mn^{III} to Mn^{II} . The cyclic voltammograms for complexes (**4-7**) are shown in Figs. 2(a-d).

Table 2. The important IR spectral bands for ohglH₂ and its complexes

Ligand/Complex	ν_{NH}	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{as(COO)}}$	$\nu_{\text{s(COO)}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ (Carboxylate)	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ (Quinol carbonyl)	ν_{COO} (Slicylate)
ohglH ₂	3452s 3186s 3073s	1634s	1545msh	1607s	1400m	-	-	-	-
[Mn ^{III} (ohglH ₃)] (1)	3436s 3600- 2500sbr	1641s	1515msh	1590s	1400m	480s	280w	-	-
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(sal)(H ₂ O)] (2)	3429s	-	1507s	1600s	1394m	514s	247m	369w	1354s
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(nic)(H ₂ O)] (3)	3443sbr	1621s	1524m	1600s	1370s	455s	278m 297m	356w	1348s
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(sal)(py)] (4)	3440s	1625ssh	1523ssh	1595s	1381s	487m	254s	387w	1357s
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O (5)	3415s	1636vs	1537s	1586ssh	1367s	498w	275m	-	1367ss
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(py) ₂].iI ₂ O (6)	3462vs	1692vs	-	1598ssh	1391ssh	521m	271m	-	1029m
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(3-pic) ₂].H ₂ O (7)	3462vs	1692vs 1640s	1540ssh	1600s	1394s	521m	274m	-	1361s

Table 3. Electronic spectral data for ohglH₂ and its manganese(III) complexes

Ligand/Complex	Electronic spectral bands λ_{max} (nm) (ϵ_{max} dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)
ohglH ₂	298 (4870), 403 (5710), 490 (6050)
[Mn ^{III} (ohglH ₃)] (1)	458 (138), 560 (160)
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(sal)(H ₂ O)] (2)	293 (2066), 329 (1280), 492 (662), 544 (596)
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(nic)(H ₂ O)] (3)	285 (2739), 483 (470), 544 (435)
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(sal)(py)] (4)	480 (760), 541 (395)
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O (5)	325 (1300), 445 (790), 546 (560)
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(py) ₂].H ₂ O (6)	293 (1283), 310 (1250), 390 (630), 595 (120)
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(3-pic) ₂].H ₂ O (7)	290 (7130), 329 (1548), 337 (440), 486 (192), 589 (248)

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate, glycine, 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde were AnalaR or GR (E. Merck) quality reagents. All other chemicals were of reagent grade. Reagent grade organic solvents were dried and purified by recommended procedures⁴⁰ before their use.

Metal content was determined by a standard literature method⁴¹. C, H and N were determined microanalytically at SAIF, NEHU, Shillong on a Microanalyzer Heracus

Fig. 2(a). [Mn^{III}(ohgl)(sal)(py)] (4).

Fig. 2(b). [Mn^{III}(ohgl)(ohdtb)(H₂O)₂].H₂O (5).

Fig. 2(c). $[Mn^{III}(ohgl)(ohdtb)(py)_2] \cdot H_2O$ (6).

Fig. 2(d). $[Mn^{III}(ohgl)(ohdtb)(3-pic)_2] \cdot H_2O$ (7).

Carlo Erba 1108. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a Faraday electro-balance using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as the calibrant. The molar conductances of the complexes at 10^{-3} M dilution in methanol were determined by using a Direct Reading Conductivitymeter-304 model with dip-type conductivity cell (Systronics). Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-983 spectrophotometer in the range $4000-450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in KBr discs and in the range $600-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in CsI discs. The 1H NMR spectra were recorded on EM-90, 90 MHz spectrometer in $DMSO-d_6$ using TMS as internal standard. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Spectroscan UV-2600, Double beam UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Chemito). Electrochemical measurements were performed under dry nitrogen atmosphere using an ECDA model and BAS CV-IB cyclic Voltammograph with X-Y recorder model RE 0089, EG

& G Princeton Applied Research, with a three-electrode cell using 0.1 M tetra-*n*-butylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as the supporting electrolyte.

Preparation of ligands and complexes :

Preparation of N-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine (ohglH₂) :

In order to prepare *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine, 25 mL hot water solution containing glycine (1.0 g, 13 mmol) was refluxed with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (2.29 g, 13 mmol) dissolved in ethanol (50 mL) for about 2 h which yielded reddish brown polycrystalline precipitate. It was purified by repeated washing with aqueous-ethanol (1 : 2) and dried *in vacuo* over fused $CaCl_2$. The melting point of the ligand was found $120\text{ }^\circ C$. (Found (%) : C, 68.12; H, 4.80; N, 6.11; Calcd. (%) : C, 68.20; H, 4.86; N, 6.20 for $C_{13}H_{11}NO_3$). The potassium salt of this ligand has been reported in literature³⁴.

Preparation of sodium salt of o-hydroxydithiobenzoate (ohdtbNa) :

A solution of *o*-hydroxy benzaldehyde (21 mL, ~25 g) in 60 ml of ethanol was heated to $65\text{ }^\circ C$ and 135 mL of the filtered ammonium polysulfide was added in 10 mL portions during 10 min keeping temperature at $65\text{ }^\circ C$. The reaction mixture was boiled to reflux for 1 h, immediately cooled in ice, 100 ml of ether was added and the solution was acidified with conc. HCl. The dithioacid, which separated as red oil, was filtered through suction to remove precipitated sulfur. The filtrate was transferred into a separating funnel, 100 ml of ether was also added and the ethereal layer containing the dithioacid was separated and washed with distilled water. The red coloured sodium salt of the dithioacid was extracted in 100 mL aqueous layer by shaking the ethereal solution of the dithioacid two times with aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (8%).

Preparation of [Mn(ohglH)₃] (1) [ohglH₂=N-(2-oxo-1-naphthylidene)glycine] :

A methanolic solution of ligand, ohglH₂ (1.64 g, 7 mmol, 25 mL) was added dropwise with stirring to a 25 mL methanolic solution containing manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.50 g, 2 mmol) at $60\text{ }^\circ C$. The resulting deep-brown coloured solution was stirred for 1 h and finally the volume was reduced to 30 mL under vacuum. The precipitate thus obtained was suction filtered, washed with methanol, recrystallized from acetonitrile and dried *in vacuo* over fused $CaCl_2$.

Table 4. Cyclic voltammetric data

Complexes	E_{pa} (V)	E_{pc} (V)	E_{RT}^0 (V) (ΔE_p , (V)) Mn ^{III} -Mn ^{II}
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(sal)(py)] (4)	-	-0.340	-
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O (5)	-0.408	-0.480	-0.444 (0.072)
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(py) ₂].H ₂ O (6)	-0.245	-0.418	-0.332 (0.173)
[Mn ^{III} (ohgl)(ohdtb)(3-pic) ₂].H ₂ O (7)	-0.443	-0.527	-0.485 (0.084)

$E_{RT} = 1/2 [E_{pc} + E_{pa}]$, $\Delta E = E_{pc} - E_{pa}$.

Preparation of (Mn(ohgl)(L)(H₂O)] (ohglH₂ = N-(2-oxo-1-naphthylidene)glycine); L = salicylate (sal) (2)/4-nicotinate (nic) (3) :

A methanolic solution of ohglH₂ (0.70 g, 3 mmol, 25 mL) was added gradually with stirring to 25 mL methanolic solution containing manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.50 g, 2 mmol) at 60 °C and the solution was stirred for 1 h. To this resulting solution, 25 mL methanolic solution of potassium salicylate (1.08 g, 6 mmol)/potassium 4-nicotinate (0.99 g, 6 mmol) was added dropwise and magnetically stirred for 1 h which yielded brown coloured precipitate. The precipitate was suction filtered, washed with methanol, recrystallized from acetonitrile and dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl₂.

Preparation of [Mn(ohgl)(sal)(py)] (4) [py = pyridine] :

To a deep brown coloured solution, obtained by gradual addition and stirring of methanolic solution of ohglH₂ (0.70 g, 3 mmol, 25 mL) to a 25 mL methanolic solution of manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.50 g, 2 mmol) at 60 °C, pyridine (0.48 g, 6 mmol) was added followed by addition of potassium salicylate (1.08 g, 6 mmol) with stirring. The resulted precipitate was suction filtered, washed with methanol and dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl₂.

Preparation of (Mn(ohgl)(ohdtb)(A)₂].H₂O (5-7) [ohdtb = o-hydroxydithiobenzoate; A = H₂O, pyridine (py) or 3-picoline (3-pic)] :

[Mn(ohgl)(ohdtb)(H₂O)₂].H₂O (5) was prepared similar to the complex (2), by using sodium o-hydroxydithiobenzoate (1.18 g, 6 mmol) instead of potassium salicylate. [Mn(ohgl)(ohdtb)(py/3-pic)₂].H₂O (6,7) was prepared similar to the complex (4) using pyridine (0.48 g, 6 mmol) or 3-picoline (0.57 g, 6 mmol) and sodium o-hydroxydithiobenzoate (1.18 g, 6 mmol) instead of potassium salicylate. The complexes thus obtained were suction filtered, washed with methanol, recrystallized from acetonitrile and dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl₂.

Fig. 3. Compound (1).

Fig. 4. Compounds (2, 3).

Fig. 5. Compound (4).

Fig. 6. Compounds (5-7).

X = H₂O (5), py (6), 3-pic (7)

Conclusions :

Based on stoichiometries and the physico-chemical studies octahedral coordination around manganese(III) have been proposed. The tentatively proposed structures of

these complexes are shown in Figs. 3–6.

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